

Crushing analysis and crashworthiness optimization design of Reinforced Regular Hexagon Honeycomb Sandwich Panel

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ABSTRACT

Honeycomb sandwich panels (HSP) have exhibited significant advantages in light weight and energy absorption and they have been widely applied in automotive, aerospace, transportation and defense industries. Rather than restating details of the existing standard regular hexagon HSP (R0-HSP), this paper introduces single-rib reinforced regular hexagon HSP (R1-HSP) and double-rib reinforced regular hexagon HSP (R2-HSP). The mechanical characteristics of these three structures are first investigated by series full-scale elaborator models through LS-DYNA. It is found that the R1-HSP has the best crashworthiness performance under axial impact regarding specific energy absorption per unit ($SEAm$) when the peak crashing stress (σ_{peak}) is less important. Secondly, the thickness matching effect between stiffener and cell-wall is analyzed with equivalent apparent density index to evaluate the contribution of the change of deformation model to the general mechanical properties. Consequently, the 2.0 times and 1.5 times of the stiffener thickness to that of cell-wall are found to be the most optimal options for R1-HSP and R2-HSP respectively. To optimize the crashworthiness of the R1-HSP, optimal Latin hypercube design (OLHD) method is used for selection of sampling design points in the design space. And in the meantime, an accurate surrogate modeling method, or, more specifically named as response surface method (RSM), is adopted to formulate the $SEAm$ and σ_{peak} functions. The results yielded from the optimization indicate that the R1-HSP is superior to R0-HSP in $SEAm$ under the same limitation of σ_{peak} . This research is significant in providing technical support in the extended applications of different HSPs used as crashworthiness structures, and it has essential reference value in low volume and low mass energy absorber design.

1 INTRODUCTION

To better understand crashworthiness behaviors of HSP structures, comprehensive studies have been conducted by analytical, numerical, and experimental methods. These studies mainly focused on the failure mechanisms, impact force, damage initiation and damage propagation of sandwich panels impacted by a solid, round-shaped or truncated cone impactor[1-3]. To investigate the energy-absorption characteristics of sandwich panels, Goldsmith and Sackman[4] described an experiment study of both bare honeycomb cores (HCs) and HSPs under the impact loading of blunt strikers. However, impact behavior of the HSP is dominated by the deformation of the HC, which gets crushed as transverse stresses become large. The mechanical characteristics of the HC deformation are decisive factors for the energy absorption capability of the HSP [5]. Mcfarland [6] first presented a semi-

empirical model to predict the crushing stress of hexagonal cell structures subjected to axial loading. Ashby [7] systematically analyzed both the in-plane and the out-of-plane crash properties of honeycomb structures. De Oliveira and Wierzbicki[8], Wierzbicki [9], Wierzbicki and Abramowicz[10] proposed a super folding theory for predicting the mean crushing strength of thin-walled structures. Wu and Jiang [11] compared the predictions based on the theory by Wierzbicki and co-workers against the quasi-static compression test results on honeycombs.

As an energy absorber, the HSP is expected to absorb as much impact energy as possible per unit mass or volume, especially when used in aerospace system. Designing optimization using non-linear tools for evaluating the objective and constraints is expensive and time consuming. In design process, statistical methods are incorporated to enhance the effects of changing various parameters in order to optimize the crashworthiness characteristics. Therefore, meta-models are developed as surrogates of the expensive simulation processes for model approximation, optimization and design space exploration [12]. Hou et al. [13] discovered factors that have remarkable effects on the crashworthiness of the HSP.

Due to the restrictions of production capacity, even the “mature” product-hexagon honeycomb, there is still a certain gap to the energy absorption requirements of large-tonnage impact, such as re-entry capsule and high-speed trains. How to improve the energy absorption ability of the HSP with standard hexagon HC have always drawn the researchers’ attention. Some foreign companies which manufacture honeycomb products, such as HEXCEL [14], had launched honeycomb products with reinforcement. Based on the standard hexagon honeycomb, aluminum with different thicknesses is bonded between wavelike sheets to achieve significantly better performances.

In this study, series full-scale elaborator HSP models with regular hexagon aluminum HC of different geometric configurations reinforced with stiffeners are constructed based on explicit nonlinear finite element numerical simulation analysis method to study their mechanical properties. Besides, the thickness matching effects between stiffener and cell-wall are studied for different kinds of stiffener thickness combinations. The influence of the stiffener thickness to the general buckling model is analyzed with equivalent apparent density index to evaluate the contribution of the deformation model change to the general mechanical properties. Then, optimal Latin hypercube design (OLHD) of experiments method is used to determine the sampling design points. Also based on the design of experiments (DOE) results, the RSM is used to build surrogate models that relate $SEAm$ and σ_{peak} to the geometric design variables after the study of thickness matching effect between stiffener and cell-wall. Optimization is then carried out by using sequential quadratic optimization technique NLPQL for exhibiting the crashworthiness difference between reinforced HSP and unreinforced HSP, thereby showing the advantage of reinforced HSP for potential engineering applications.

2 CRASHWORTHINESS INDICATORS

In order to study and compare the crashworthiness of the HSP, it is essential to define the crashworthiness indicators. There are many different indicators available to evaluate the energy absorption capabilities of different structures [15]. Specific energy absorption (SEA) is usually used to estimate the energy absorption capacity of absorbers among these indicators. The SEA is defined as the amount of absorbed energy absorbed by per unit mass of the structure and can be formulated as follows [16]:

$$SEA_m = \frac{E_{total}}{M} = \frac{\int_0^{\delta} F(\delta)d\delta}{M} \quad (1)$$

Where δ is the axial crushing distance, M is the total mass of the structure and E_{total} is total absorbed energy by the HSP during crushing, V is the volume of the honeycomb structure, $F(\delta)$ is the axial crushing force.

For the safe design of energy absorbers, σ_{peak} should be reduced or constrained under certain level [16]. Consequently, σ_{peak} is considered as an essential crashworthiness indicator. It is defined as,

$$\sigma_{peak} = PCF / A_0 \quad (2)$$

3 FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

The nonlinear explicit FE code LS-DYNA 971 is used to simulate the crushing behavior and energy-absorbing capability of the impacted HSP with single-rib or double-rib HC. Fig. 1 is the schematic diagram of HSP under out-of-plane impact, in which the HSP is placed between two rigid plates. The lower plate is fully fixed, forming the supporting platform for the impacting, while the upper one falls at a speed of 10m/s, which is typically encountered in passenger vehicle crash event [17]. H_{f1} , H_{f2} and H_c denotes the upper face sheet thickness, lower face sheet thickness and HC height respectively.

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of HSP under axial impact

Figure 2: Geometric configuration of honeycomb

Three different core cell configurations with regular hexagon honeycomb (R0), single-rib reinforced (R1) and double-rib reinforced regular hexagon honeycomb (R2) are illustrated in Fig. 2, where t_0 is the wall thickness of the hexagon honeycomb cell, l is length of honeycomb cell edge, t_1 is the thickness of the stiffener, a is total length, b is total width. The basic geometrical parameters of these three HSPs with different configurations are given as $H_{f1}=H_{f2}=1\text{mm}$, $l=4\text{mm}$, $t_0=t_1=0.06\text{mm}$, $H_c=60\text{mm}$, $a=44\text{mm}$, $b=34.64\text{mm}$. All walls are modeled using the Belytschko-Tsay four-node shell elements. An automatic single-surface contact algorithm is defined to account for the contact of the column itself during deformation, while an automatic node-to-surface contact is used between HSP and rigid wall. For both static and dynamic friction, the friction coefficient of 0.2 is adopted for all contact condition. The face sheets and the HCs are made of Al-2024 aluminum alloy [18] and 5052-O aluminum alloy [19] respectively. And accordingly they are defined as bilinear, isotropic, plastic materials, the properties of which are presented in Table.1.

Property	Face sheets (Al-2024 aluminum alloy)	Honeycomb core (5052-o aluminum alloy)
ρ_0 (kg/m ³)	2700	2685
E (GPa)	72.4	69.6
E_T (GPa)	28	2.5
σ_y (MPa)	75.8	65.5
ν	0.33	0.33

Table 1: Material properties for HSPs

3.1 Straightforward comparison of mechanical capacities

Fig.3 shows dynamic response results of HSPs in different configurations. σ denotes nominal stress and it is defined as,

$$\sigma = F(\delta) / A_0 \quad (3)$$

The nominal strain is defined as follows,

$$\varepsilon = \delta / H_c \quad (4)$$

Figure 3: Stress-strain response curves of HSPs at 10m/s

From Fig.3, it is clear that the out-of-plane compression of HSPs with reinforced HC are the same as the HSP with regular HC which can be characterized by three stages: viz. a short elastic stage, a long plateau stage and finally a densification stage. It can be found that the plateau stress on the compression process (under the condition of $0.7 \geq \varepsilon \geq 0.15$) is stable. So this process is the most important one in engineering application.

Fig.4 shows a straightforward comparison of mechanical capacities of the three HSP designs. As shown in Fig.4, $SEAm$ and σ_{peak} increase as t_0 increase for each kind of HSP. And the $SEAm$ and σ_{peak} of R1-HSP or R2-HSP are higher than that of R0-HSP. Compared with that of R0-HSP when

$t_0=t_1=0.08\text{mm}$, the $SEAm$ of R1-HSP increase by 56.32%. As t_0 increases, the $SEAm$ of R1-HSP is almost the same as that of R2-HSP and even outstrips R2-HSP when $t_0=t_1=0.1\text{mm}$. Therefore for some cases in which the σ_{peak} is less important, R1-HSP is reasonably recommended for the buffer structural design to improve the energy absorption capacity without exceeding the restricted σ_{peak} .

Figure 4: Comparison of crashworthiness indicators of the three HSP designs

3.2 Study of the thickness matching effect Title

According to the study in Section 3.1, the stiffeners do indeed improve the energy absorption capacity of the HSP. However, this process will cause the change of structure stiffness. To analyze the influence of stiffness change to the mechanical property of the HSP, full-scale elaborator models for three kinds of HSPs in different thicknesses of t_1 are constructed for direct numerical simulation.

Figure 5: Stress-strain response curves of HSPs with different t_1

The stress-strain curves of R1-HSP and R2-HSP are shown in Fig.5. It can be distinguished that for R1-HSP the plateau stress is relatively stable as $t_1 \leq 2.0t_0$. The fluctuation of plateau stress becomes apparent while $t_1 > 2.0t_0$. Similar to this mechanical property of R1-HSP, R2-HSP also seems to have a “separation point” when $t_1 > 1.5t_0$, due to the reason that as $t_1 > 1.5t_0$, the stress-strain curve of R2-HSP fluctuates substantially. To further determine the “separation points” for R1-HSP and R2-HSP, Table 2 gives the values of peak-to-peak stress at plateau stage. These values of peak-to-peak stress denote the differences between the maximum stress and the minimum stress at plateau stage (from $\epsilon = 0.15$ to $\epsilon = 0.7$).

Type	$t_1=0.5 t_0$	$t_1=1.0 t_0$	$t_1=1.5 t_0$	$t_1=2.0 t_0$	$t_1=2.5 t_0$	$t_1=3 t_0$
R1-HSP/MPa	0.19	0.17	0.21	0.24	0.82	0.79
R2-HSP/MPa	0.13	0.16	0.24	0.91	0.96	1.26

Table 2: Comparison between peak-to-peak stress at plateau stage

For R1-HSP, the value of peak-to-peak stress increases by nearly 3.4 times as t_1 increases from $2.0 t_0$ to $2.5 t_0$. Meanwhile, the value of peak-to-peak stress increases by nearly 3.8 times as t_1 increases from $1.5 t_0$ to $2.0 t_0$ for R2-HSP. Therefore, by analyzing the stress-strain curves of impact end, it can be concluded that the “separation points” are $2.0t_0$ and $1.5t_0$ for the two types of reinforced HSP respectively.

3.3 Evaluation of matching effect by equivalent apparent density index

There is an obvious “turning point” in the choice of the thickness of stiffener, and so is the influence by changing the stiffener thickness to the mechanical property of HSP. However, this is just from the apparent reflection of fluctuation phenomenon and plateau strength. Hereby it is necessary to use equivalent apparent density index to evaluate the contribution of stiffener in the general mechanical properties. In this essay, the relative error of mechanical characteristics deduced by adopting equivalent apparent density index was used as criteria. Keeping the value of apparent density of the HC unchanged, the HC with different thicknesses of stiffener ($t_1 \neq t_0$) is equivalent to uniform reinforced HC in which t_1 is the same as t_0 . If the other two geometric parameters (viz. $H_{f1}=H_{f2}=1\text{mm}$, $l=4\text{mm}$) of HSP keep constant, then the respective equivalent thicknesses of R1-HSP and R2-HSP, t_1^* and t_2^* , can be formulated as follows

$$t_1^* = (3t_1 + 8t_0) / 11 \quad (5)$$

$$t_2^* = (6t_1 + 8t_0) / 14 \quad (6)$$

The relative errors η_p and η_{SEA} are indicator factors to evaluate the matching performance of HSP with unequal thickness. They can be calculated by:

$$\eta_p = 100 \times (\sigma_{peak}^* - \sigma_{peak}) / \sigma_{peak}^* \quad (7)$$

$$\eta_{SEA} = 100 \times (SEA_m^* - SEA_m) / SEA_m^* \quad (8)$$

Where σ_{peak}^* and SEA_m^* denote the peak compression stress and specific energy absorption of HSP with HC after equivalent treatment.

	Reinforced with t_1			Reinforced with equivalent t^*			Different rate	
	t_1/mm	$SEAm /$	$\sigma_{peak} / \text{MPa}$	t^*/mm	$SEAm^* /$	$\sigma_{peak}^* / \text{MPa}$	η_{SEA}	η_p
R1-HSP	0.03	5.4105	2.7714	0.05182	5.7638	2.7202	6.13	1.88
	0.06	6.2685	3.3468	0.06000	6.2685	3.3468	0	0
	0.09	6.8581	3.8999	0.06818	7.4715	3.9989	8.21	2.47
	0.12	7.4221	4.5336	0.07636	8.2221	4.4877	9.73	1.02
	0.15	7.8869	5.1399	0.08455	10.3257	5.2239	23.62	1.61
	0.18	8.2685	5.7310	0.09273	11.6474	5.6897	29.01	0.72
R2-HSP	0.03	5.4994	3.0541	0.04714	6.0399	3.0187	8.95	1.17
	0.06	6.3132	3.9254	0.06000	6.3132	3.9254	0	0
	0.09	6.9135	4.8105	0.07286	7.6339	4.9043	9.44	1.91
	0.12	7.3914	5.7054	0.08571	9.4121	5.8248	21.47	2.05
	0.15	7.8395	6.6227	0.09857	11.1135	6.7434	29.46	1.79
	0.18	7.7884	7.4644	0.11143	13.2108	7.3932	41.09	0.96

Table 3: Comparison on mechanical properties before and after equivalent treatment

The results are listed in Table 3. The values of η_p are so small that they can be neglected. While the values of η_{SEA} are relatively large thus can not. For the R1-HSP, the value of η_{SEA} jumped from 9.73% to 23.62% when $t_1 > 2.0t_0$. This significant mutation of η_{SEA} also can be found when $t_1 > 1.5t_0$ for R2-HSPs. Specifically, when $t_1 = 2.0t_0$, the η_{SEA} can be as much as 21.47%. However, the matching effect is not that

ideal for R2-HSP as $t_1 = 2t_0$. For this reason, the conclusion that $t_1 = 2t_0$ and $t_1 = 1.5t_0$ are the “separation points” for R1-HSP and R2-HSP respectively is demonstrated by the introduction of equivalent apparent density index.

4 DESIGN OPTIMIZATION

4.1 Optimization problem set-up

Based on the previous analysis, knowledge about the mechanical properties of the three kinds of HSPs and the thickness matching effect of the R1-HSP and R2-HSP have been realized. It is concluded that R1-HSP has significant potential and seems to be superior and ideal to the crashworthiness design. However, as an energy absorber, the HSP is expected to absorb as much impact energy as possible per unit mass or volume, especially when used in aerospace system. On the other hand, σ_{peak} of the structure is also an important indicator for the safety of the crushed object. σ_{peak} of the structure should be constrained under a certain level. In this section, energy absorption optimizations of the HSP have been achieved under the same constraint of σ_{peak} , which was used in Ref. [20]. Thus the optimization problem can be formulated as follows:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \max \quad SEAm \\ s.t. \quad \sigma_{peak} \leq 1.21MPa \\ \quad \quad 0.02mm \leq t_0 \leq 0.1mm \\ \quad \quad 0.5mm \leq H_f \leq 2mm \\ \quad \quad 4mm \leq l \leq 10mm \end{array} \right. \quad (9)$$

During the optimization process, we assume that $H_{f1}=H_{f2}=H_f$ and choose $t_1 = 2.0t_0$ for R1-HSP.

4.2 Optimization and comparison of R0-HSP and R1-HSP

Meta-model-based optimization is used to create and optimize an approximate model of the design instead of optimizing the design through direct simulation. Once the meta-model has been built, it can be used to find the optimum. In order to achieve optimized response for the HSP under axial impact loading, the surrogate model approach, e.g. RSM, is used which has been proven to be particularly effective under such circumstance [20]. In this study, RSM is employed to predict the crashworthiness indices of $SEAm$, $SEAv$ and σ_{peak} of the HSP under axial impact loading.

It is essential to examine whether the fitted model provides an adequate approximation to the true response surface. To check the accuracy of the fitted model, the root mean square error (RMSE), R^2 and the relative error (RE) are applied to evaluate the meta-model's accuracy respectively, which can be written as [21-23]:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_{val}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{val}} D(y_i - y_i^r)^2} \quad (10)$$

$$RE = \frac{y_i - y_i^r}{y_i} \quad (11)$$

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m (y_i - y_i^r)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^m (y_i - \bar{y}_i^r)^2} \quad (12)$$

where N_{val} is the number of validation points. y_i and y_i^r are the FEA result and the approximate result by meta-model respectively. RMSE is used to gauge the overall accuracy of the model, while

RE is used to gauge the local accuracy of the model. The smaller the values of RMSE and RE, the more accurate the meta-model will be. R^2 measures the suitability of the model and shows whether the variation is acceptable, and it lies in the interval $[0, 1]$. The closer the R^2 is to the upper bound, the better the estimation of the response. A low value of R^2 usually means that the region of interest is either too large or too small and the gradients are not trustworthy [24]. The mathematic optimization method used in this paper is nonlinear programming by quadratic approximation of the Lagrangian (NLPQL) [25]. In order to establish the meta-models of $SEAm$, $SEAv$ and σ_{peak} for R0-HSP and R1-HSP, 32 initial design points are sampled respectively using the optimal Latin hypercube design (OLHD) method [26].

In order to evaluate the accuracies of the meta-models, additional 16 points are used. In the process of generating these RS models, the polynomials are selected as the basis functions. By using Eq.(10)–(12), the accuracy evaluation indicators of different polynomial functions (i.e. $SEAm$, $SEAv$ and σ_{peak}) whose orders range from 1 to 4 are predicted under axial load impact, and they are summarized in Tables 4-5.

		Poly 1	Poly 2	Poly 3	Poly 4
$SEAm$	RMSE	0.04057	0.02937	0.02849	0.02346
	R^2	0.8795	0.94538	0.97526	0.9017
	RE(%)	-0.412-0.435	-0.345-0.556	-0.388-0.254	-0.714-0.517
σ_{peak}	RMSE	0.203	0.165	0.1858	0.1727
	R^2	0.89401	0.95503	0.9391	0.94566
	RE(%)	-1.124-2.756	-1.143-2.166	-1.273-2.386	-1.042-3.417

Table 4: Accuracy of different polynomial RSM models for R0-HSP

		Poly 1	Poly 2	Poly 3	Poly4
$SEAm$	RMSE	0.0461	0.0534	0.0468	0.0489
	R^2	0.8698	0.88507	0.93043	0.9078
	RE(%)	-0.201-0.186	-0.215-0.229	-0.198-0.215	-0.191-0.281
σ_{peak}	RMSE	0.4057	0.3133	0.3587	0.396
	R^2	0.89747	0.95507	0.92043	0.93615
	RE(%)	-2.349-3.014	-2.321-2.459	-2.546-2.981	-3.091-2.503

Table5: Accuracy of different polynomial RSM models for R1-HSP

The optimization problem is obtained and the optimal designs are shown in Table 6. It can be found that the errors between FEA results and the approximation results based on meta-models are all less than 5%. This indicates that the approximation functions for R0-HSP and R1-HSP responses under axial compression are accurate. As summarized in these tables, the R1-HSP has better performance than the R0-HSP in terms of $SEAm$. Compared with R0-HSP, the $SEAm$ for R1-HSP increases 12.9% under the same limitation of σ_{peak} .

Type	Foil thickness t_o /mm	Cell length l /mm	Face sheet H_f /mm	$SEAm$ (KJ/kg)		
				Meta-model	FEA	Error (%)
R0-HSP	0.0458	4.625	0.5	4.812	4.953	2.847
R1-HSP	0.0577	7.431	0.5	5.434	5.671	4.179

Table 6: Optimal results under σ_{peak} constraint (1.21MPa)

5 CONCLUSION

This paper proposes the single-rib regular hexagon honeycomb sandwich panel (R1-HSP) and double-rib regular hexagon honeycomb sandwich panel (R2-HSP) based on the structure of standard regular hexagon honeycomb sandwich panel (R0-HSP). The load levels and energy absorption

capability of HSP can be greatly improved by reinforcement treatment. R1-HSP is recommended for the buffer structural design to improve the energy absorption capacity without exceeding the restricted σ_{peak} , however in some cases σ_{peak} is less important.

The thickness of stiffener is a key to the load level and energy absorption capability of HSP. However, there are some matching effects between the thickness of stiffener and cell wall. "Separation point" is found in this research by introducing equivalent apparent density index. When the thickness of stiffener is less than 2.0 times thicker and 1.5 times thicker for R1-HSP and R2-HSP respectively, the plateau stress of stress-strain curves is flush and complete. The mechanical response mutates and the fluctuation of plateau stress increases sharply as the stiffener thickness increases. So 2.0 times thicker and 1.5 times thicker are the best options in the design of R1-HSP and R2-HSP respectively.

To find the optimal design, the design optimization using response surface method (RSM) together with NLPQL algorithm have been presented. The results yielded from the optimization demonstrate that, in general, the R1-HSP is superior to R0-HSP in *SEAm* under the same limitation of σ_{peak} . It is concluded that R1-HSP structure is of considerable implications and benefits with significant potential in crashworthiness applications.

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